

The Origin Emergence and Emergence of the Sultans of the Ayyubid and Mamluk Bahri State and the Characteristics of their political Maturity (567 - 784 AH / 1171 - 1382 AD)

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Abstract

Praise be to God, who says in his dear book (We raise the ranks of whomever We will, and above all those with all-knowing knowledge) and may blessings and peace be upon our Master Muhammad and his family and companions: with much peace, and then. The Ayyubid state arose in the year (567 AH / 1171 AD) in the midst of the struggle against the Crusaders, the effect of the commitment of its founder Salah al-Din al-Ayyubi to the policy of jihad against them. The justifications for its existence and the permanence of its jihad arose, as in the event in the Battle of Hattin in (583 AH / 1187 AD) and the liberation of Jerusalem from the defilement of the Crusaders.

However, the successors of Salah Al-Din Al-Ayyubi failed to complete the historical role on which their state was based, so the matter of their jihad against the Crusaders ceased after him, and the reason for that dispute that erupted between his successors from the Ayyubid house and then the Ayyubid state was torn and divided among them, and they began directing their energies and their political and military capabilities to the fighting Among them, they abandoned their primary role in confronting the Crusaders and preferred to abide by the policy of appeasement. Some of them even resorted to the help of the forces surrounding them from the Crusaders, Khwarezmians, and Seljuks of Rome against each other to dismember their state.

In the midst of those conflicts and events, and as a result of the Seventh Crusade, a new force emerged to take its role in the events, which is the power of the Maritime Mamluks, which proved its ability to confront the Crusaders in Egypt, and even resolved many of the issues that the Ayyubid state was going through, and it became possible for the Mamluks to occupy an important role In the military and political history, which was reflected in the various aspects of life, and they were the mainstay of the army and its striking force, which increased their activities and influence on the political scene during that era. Therefore, it is necessary to give something about the origin and emergence of these two states, in order for them to take upon themselves to leave a strategic impact for those who lived through them and those who were affected by them.

Introduction

The study dealt with two topics:

The first topic: The lineage and emergence of the Ayyubid family and the characteristics of political maturity (567-648 AH / 1171-1250 AD).

The second topic: The Bahri Mamluks and their names, origins and appearances on the stage of the Abbasid Caliphate (648 - 784 AH - 1250 -1382 AD).

The first topic

The lineage and emergence of the Ayyubid family and the characteristics of political maturity

First: The lineage of the Ayyubid family

In the beginning, the Ayyubids, in the eyes of historians and researchers, represented a new political and ideological situation, especially as it was based on the aftermath of the Fatimid rule (297-567 AH / 909-1171 AD), since the end of the seventh decade of the sixth century AH, twelfth century AD, Egypt moved from the rule of the Fatimids, To a new rule represented by the rule of a new family, which assumed its rule over the country, for nearly eight decades, namely, the Ayyubid family, (567-648 AH / 1171-1250 AD)

Its first sultan was Salah al-Din al-Ayyubi, Yusuf ibn Ayyub Shadi, (d. 589 AH / 1185 AD), who represented the basis for this transformation, through his success in his position as vizier, to the Fatimid Caliph al-A'adid

Billah (1) (555-567 AH/ 1171-1171 AD) to end the caliphate The Fatimids, and the establishment of a new authority in their place, especially since it actually began (569 AH / 1165 AD) when Salah al-Din acquired the splendor of the Sultanate, which ended in 648 AH / 1250 AD, after the rule of Sultan Turan Shah (2), the last of the sultans of the Ayyubid house, which lasted His rule was for three months, which ended with his death and the ascension of his father's widow (Shajar al-Durr) (3), the reins of power, after which the Mamluk Bahri state began (648-784 AH/1250-1382 AD)

The Ayyubids belong to Najm al-Din Ayyub (4), the father of Salah al-Din, who worked in the service of the Zangids in Mosul (5), as the rule of Baalbek was assigned to him, after it was conquered by the Zangids, in 534 AH / 1148 AD) (6)

Apparently, the establishment of the pillars of the Ayyubid states in Egypt was the result of sending Nur al-Din Zangi (7) to Asad al-Din Sherkwah (8), and his nephew Salah al-Din to Egypt, in order to get rid of the Crusader occupation (9)

There are historians, who traced the lineage of the Ayyubids, such as Ibn Khalkan, (d. 681 AH / 1282 AD) and transmitted it to us by Ibn Katheer. He says I have followed them, repeatedly, and there is no one who mentioned any other after Shadi, and here it becomes clear the lineage of Ayub bin Shadi and Sherkwah bin Shadi (10)

On the cusp of this, when the Fatimid ministry was assigned to Asad al-Din Sherkwah, Salah al-Din was appointed as a vizier after the death of his uncle, in the same year (564 AH / 1168 AD), by the Fatimid Caliph al-A'idh (555-567 AH / 1160-1171 AD) (11)

Salah El-Din worked, from the moment of his position, to control the administration of the entire country of Egypt, so he sent someone to summon his father and brothers, with the approval of Nouredine, Who walked with them, a special guard to protect them (12)

Second: The emergence of the Ayyubid dynasty on the stage of political events

Istizar was accompanied by Salah al-Din, many of the actions that he carried out, which lead to the consolidation of the foundations of his authority, and work to weaken the Fatimid Caliphate, and sought to overthrow it, so he began to get rid of all the hostile elements, which may pose a threat to his political future, so he formed a special group that he called the authority (13), which is a group of soldiers affiliated with Sultan Salah al-Din, whose duties include protecting him and carrying out military duties, and he made, Prince Abu al-Hija, its commander, (14), and he also benefited from the Turkish soldiers to confront his enemies inside (15)

With all these precautions, which Salah al-Din worked on, as he tried hard to confront them, he was exposed to conspiracies from the Sudanese soldiers, and their leader is the trusted caliph (16)

But soon Salah al-Din al-Ayyubi killed them, killed their leader, and ordered their expulsion from Egypt (17)

Among the movements and strife, a strong movement emerged, led by the poet 'Amara al-Yamani (18), who praised the Fatimid Caliphate. From here it seems that 'Amara al-Yamani was keen to restore the rule of the Fatimids, by counting the Ayyubids, usurpers of the Fatimid throne, especially as he described Salah. Religion, with the title of the Little King (19)

It seems that the level of external dangers was not absent from the scene of events, especially when the Yemeni architecture cooperated with the Byzantines against the Ayyubid presence, especially after the King of Sicily William II sent a large army in (570 AH / 1174 AD) that managed to occupy Alexandria, but Soon Saladin was able to expel them, in the same year (20)

The joint Byzantine Crusade also came, as it appears that it targeted Damietta in the year (565 AH/ 1169 AD), after he asked for help and ammunition from Nur al-Din (21), and Damietta managed to resist and the campaign failed, against it (22)

Salah al-Din managed, after these events in particular, in the year (567 AH/ 1171 AD), to overthrow the Fatimid Caliphate, and from that moment on, Egypt became dependent on Baghdad, where the Abbasid Caliphate(23)

It seems that Salah al-Din was ruling Egypt on behalf of Nur al-Din Mahmoud Zangi, until his death in the year 569 AH / 1173 AD, when his son, the good king Ismail (24)

From here came the policy of Salah Al-Din towards this event, he decided to go to the Levant, and announced his support and sponsorship to the righteous king, to manage the affairs of his kingdom,

It seems that he succeeded in subjugating Aleppo(25), Mosul and the Euphrates Island, within a short period of time (26)

The writings of historians indicate that Salah al-Din failed to convince the good king Ismail of his loyalty to him (27). It appears that Salah al-Din became the legitimate ruler and administrator of Egypt's affairs, and no longer ruled it on behalf of the family of Nur al-Din (28).

Third: Characteristics of the political maturity of the Ayyubid Sultanate

It seems that Salah al-Din, from the first moment of his administration of Egypt, did not hesitate to confront all his opponents, until what he wanted was achieved on the home front. One of the most important decisive battles, which constituted an important turning point for him, and for those who were with him in a battle, was Hattin (29), as this battle marked the beginning of successive victories, and from here the cities of Jableh (30), Nablus

(31), Acre (32), were handed over. Caesarea (33), Ramleh (34), Jaffa (35), Beirut (36), the cities of Arsuf (37), and the coast of Palestine (38)

Jerusalem was recovered, in the year (583 AH / 1187 AD), from the Knights of Europe, and the events that took advantage of Jerusalem were of great importance, which had a great impact on the souls of all Muslims, as it constituted a historical turning point for the future of Salah al-Din, and it became an Islamic symbol referred to as stubbornness, all This prompted the King of England Richard (39), the heart of the Lion, to accept and be satisfied, by concluding a peace treaty between them, in the city of Ramle, in the year (587 AH / 1191 AD), called the Peace of Ramla, as all cities and lands of the Levant were considered, in the hands of Salah al-Din, except Tyre (40), and Jaffa (41)

Since that time, Salah al-Din has been ruling a vast country, as the kings and rulers of Armenia and Constantinople, and others were courting him(42), until he died in (Safar 589 AH / March 1193 AD), in Damascus, and he was then 57 years old (43)

After all these bids, for Salah al-Din, his kingdom was divided after his death, among his three sons and his brother, al-Malik al-Adil, so the son of the Aziz King Uthman (44) in Egypt, and his son, King Afzal Ali (45), in Damascus, and his son, al-Malik al-Zahir (46) in Aleppo, As for his brother, Al-Malik Al-Adil (47), who ruled central and northern Iraq, and Diyar Bakr (48), where he passed to his cousins Baalbek (49), Homs (50), Hama (51), and Yemen (52)

The second topic

The Bahri Mamluks, their names, origins and appearances on the stage of the Abbasid Caliphate (648 - 784 AH - 1250 - 1382 AD)

First: - The naming of the marine Mamluks

The Mamluk era is considered one of the most historical eras, in Egypt and the Levant, for its special character, and the reason is that it was a country that arose in politically harsh conditions, because of two dangers, the Crusaders and the Mongols, so the Mamluk Maritime State was the protective shield for Muslims.

Here, I must refer to their name, as their name is mentioned in language, and Malik is an accusative noun, which was derived from the verb possess, and it is the language of the slave as it is said Fath al-lam, (a slave of a queen) and unlike it, if it is combined, it means captivity, where the king is only his parents (53)

So the owned is the slave, as the source indicated by saying, the owned is the slave, i.e. his property is the thing by possession (54), and the slave is said his parents are from the slave, while the owned is born to parents, free and sold (55)

And as the Almighty said: And your oaths do not possess, for God does not love one who is arrogant and proud (56), and there are those who describe the Mamluks with the word, (Al-Mamluk) (57)

From this it becomes clear that the linguistic expression of the word "owned" means the slave, i.e. sold and bought. As for the idiomatic meaning, it came to pertain to white slaves, and did not pertain to black slaves (58)

The Abbasid Caliphs, the first to use the Mamluks, were white slaves, and the era of the Caliph Al-Ma'mun (198 - 218 AH / 813 - 833 AD) was the first to increase the purchase of the Mamluks, from Central Asia, and expensively bought them (59)

Second: The origins of the marine Mamluks

The origins of the Maritime Mamluks go back to various peoples of different peoples, and with this matter the merchants brought this category, as the majority of them were European Christians.

And the Jews, as well as the Persians (60), and the country of the Caucasus (61), which extends to the Caspian Sea, and the Black Sea, as well as Turkestan, and the Caucasus (62), is the main home from which the Mamluks come to the territories of the Arab Islamic state, where it was indicated, Until the Turks sell their children, male and female (63), and there are also affiliated cities of the Byzantine Empire, especially those colonies, on the Black Sea, which became a popular place for selling the Mamluks, and they were brought from those areas, in addition to the city of Genoa, as it was It has a colony, called Kaffa, on the Blue Mediterranean Sea, where they traded with the Mamluks, from the Armenians and Georgians, and then their activity moved to Europe, where trade between the Arabs, Greece and others (64)

The process of bringing slaves to Egypt by the Mamluks was through the ports of Alexandria and Damietta (65) Contrasted with the Muslim merchants, who come by land, to sell the Mamelukes, who bring robes and robes (66), to the markets and Cairo, as well as to the markets of Alexandria (67)

It is clear that the sources of bringing the Mamluks to the issue of purchasing to families, or prestige, or gifts and tribute, which are paid by the military leaders, and who bring them to the slave markets, while they are still young, from several regions, in addition, from the country beyond the river, had transgressed the sources. They were a mixture or a mixture of Kurds, Turkmen, Circassians (68), Mongols and Turks (69)

In addition to the Russians and the Romans, and perhaps their affiliation with the merchants sometimes, by carrying the name of the Mamluk, the name of that merchant who brought him, to bear his title (70)

There was a custom among the marine Mamluk sultans, which was the acquisition of the best Mamluks,

To entrust them to Al-Tabbaq (71), who supervised them, and he is the one who takes care of each one of them, to his species, and all these bringers, are related to the upbringing of their well-known master, the Khushdashi (72)

Some of them are prepared educationally and militarily, and some of them are freed to join the service of their master (73)

During the rule of the Tulunid state (74), the Mamluks formed a military class, with privileges that had a future strategic dimension, on the development of events (75).

Third: The emergence of the Bahri Mamluks on the stage of the Abbasid Caliphate and the characteristics of their political maturity

With the expansion of the Mamluk phenomenon, as the sources indicated, to the presence of the Turks as Mamluks, guards inside the Abbasid court, specifically in the caliphate of Abu Jaafar al-Mansur (76), (136-158 AH / 753- 775 AD), and ascending to other caliphs, and this is confirmed by historical facts. Parts of al-Gharbiyye, which his sons, (77) were sending as money to the Caliph Abu Jaafar al-Mansur, were for boys and Turks (78)

A reference was also received from one of the sources that Caliph Al-Mansour was himself supervising the education and training of Mamluks and boys in the use of the sword, the use of arrows and throwing at it, and the teaching of other martial arts, and there is no doubt that Caliph Al-Mansour was sending Hajjaj bin Arta Al-Kufi Al-Nakh'i. (79), with his son Muhammad al-Mahdi, to the country of Khurasan to bring from it what is presented to the Caliph

Of the Mamluks (80)

Apparently, the process of preferring the Mamluks, of the Turkish race, was present, because they enjoyed the beauty of the scene and the goodness of the council, and this is in contrast to the countries, which are witnessing fierce wars (81), and which call their white slaves, in most cases, the slave trade. 82), for this matter, it was necessary to bring slaves from them, the presence and markets in the big cities, the most famous of which are in Fustat, in addition to the slave house, in Baghdad (83), especially the slave market in Damascus, and the Samarra market (84), and it seems that these procedures were motivated by the unification of rule and influence from the Abbasid Caliphs, which led to the expansion of the Mamluks' presence in most parts of the Islamic Arab state, and this was attributed to the establishment of separate and independent emirates, whether they were in the east or west (85)

The physical strength, which the Mamluks enjoyed, and many other characteristics, qualified them to have priority, at the forefront of the Abbasid armies, so they were invested in attempts to restore Abbasid control over the areas that declared independence from them, specifically in the middle of the third century AH / ninth century AD. This explains the reason for seeking the help of the Turkic kingdoms, and the exaggeration and multiplicity of them to be armies, which have a high ability to fight (86)

This matter explains the conduct of the Ikhshidid state (87), on the approach and policy of the Tulunids, especially after one of the historical sources mentioned that the Ikhshidid army of the Mamluks reached more than 400,000 ,soldiers for Egypt and the Levant) (88)

Undoubtedly, this matter was followed by the Fatimid state, which used the Mamluks, from the year 358 - 567 AH / 969-1171 AD), and it is also one of the states that raised the children of the young Mamluks, according to advanced and advanced systems, and for this reason they were called the earthly Mamluks , or stone (89)

Especially since its armies were originally from the Turkish race, which is the most important among the other races. Of course, they had the ability to lead the army and the mandate of countries, as each race had a leader, and the same goes back to after the Fatimids, who ruled Egypt and the Levant, He is Salah al-Din al-Ayyubi , founder of the Ayyubid state, in the year (567-648 AH / 1171-1250 AD), after his elimination of the Fatimid Caliphate, and by forming an army, from the Mamluks that consisted of several divisions and made the leaders over them , from the Kurds (90), and the free ones, Among these are the Nuwayri sects, according to the name of King Nur al-Din Mahmud al-Zanki, and the Asadiya after Asad al-Din Shirkuh, the uncle of Salah al -Din, and it is beyond doubt that the Salih faction, in relation to the Mamluks of Salah al-Din, and according to the conditions of the Ayyubid state, and what it went through from the attacks of the Crusaders, increased Salah al-Din. Din al-Ayyubi's need for the Mamluks until it was said that the number of Mamluks reached twelve thousand, because of their courage , high ability in fighting, and military measures, to confront the enemy (91). This matter was positively reflected on the policy of the righteous Sultan Najm al-Din Ayyub. Which he took as a method of increasing the number of Mamluk soldiers, in order to make them an impenetrable bulwark against the enemies. And the protection of the state, which made the military power of the Mamluks appear, as it was new on the political and military stage, as it appears clearly in the Ayyubid state (92)

It appears from the above, through the data, that the good Sultan Najm al-Din Ayyub wanted, through this limit, to limit the elements of the Kurds, and the algorithm (93), because they did not stand with him. This is what the Abbasid Caliph al-Mu'tasim (94) did by him, using the Mamluks, and it seemsthat there are other purposes from them, as the use of the Mamluks to decorate the processes, in the countries (95)

All these facts made the Mamluks to occupy high positions, especially during the era of the good king Najm al-Din, which became distinguished from other Kurdish princes in the Ayyubid army from the Mamluks until the sources indicate that the good king took his special guard from them and went further than that he was used by a group of The Turkish army to be guarding the vestibule (96)

The same is the case with his house and court (97), this matter made Cairo narrow, due to their large number, which made it imperative for the righteous king to expel the Mamluks to the city he ordered to build, on the island of Rawda (98)

It is the center of the new rule, for the marine Mamluks later, and he also ordered the construction of a fortress, near the Nilometer, to be with him from the year (638 AH / 1240 AD). From this work, they were named after the Bahri Mamluks (99), but the term "Salihya", synonymous with her, after the name of the good king, Najm al-Din Ayoub (100)

Conclusion

The research showed the study tagged with the title (the origin, emergence and emergence of the sultans of the Ayyubid and Mamluk Bahri state and the characteristics of their political maturity). The study concluded the following results:

1. The lineage of the Ayyubids was identified and how they appeared on the political and military stage. The origins of the Maritime Mamluks, their lineage, and how they came to the throne of the Sultanate after their remarkable increase at the end of the Ayyubid rule were studied.
2. The emergence of the Ayyubid dynasty from the first sight of Sultan Salah al-Din assuming the position of the Fatimid ministry, and with regard to the Mamluks, they appeared on the scene of the Abbasid Caliphate as a guard for the Abbasid court.
3. The study showed the characteristics of the basic maturity of the Ayyubid dynasty, which began first with the elimination of the Fatimid Caliphate, and then in the real confrontation with the Crusaders, and the recovery of Jerusalem and the rest of the other regions, but the Mamluks, according to their physical characteristics, made them to be at the forefront of the Abbasid armies, until they arrived To the most important high positions in the days of Sultan Salih Najm al-Din Ayoub, as the behaviors of political maturity showed them by excluding them with authority alone.

Margins:

1. Al-Adid Billah Al-Fatimi: He is Abu Muhammad Abdullah bin Yusuf bin Al-Hafiz bin Al-Mustansir bin Al-Zahir, nicknamed Al-Adid. He was born in (544 AH / 1149 AD), and was pledged allegiance to the Fatimid caliphate in the year 555 AH / 1160 AD. He is eleven years old after his uncle Al-Faki', and Tozeur He had Tala'i bin Razik, then he was killed, then his just son took over the ministry, and he was killed, then he took over Shawar. The Caliph Al-Adid sought the help of Sultan Nur Al-Din the martyr. Asad Al-Din Shirkuh and Salah Al-Din prepared with him. The Fatimid Caliph al-A'idh Billah died in 567 AH / 1171 AD, the last of the Fatimid caliphs in Egypt. See: Ibn Shaddad Baha al-Din Ibn Shaddad (d. 632 AH / 1234 AD), Sultan anecdotes and Al-Mahasin Yusufiya, investigation: Mahmoud Darwish, 1st edition, Publications of the Ministry of Culture, (Damascus, 1979), p. 332; Ibn Wasel, Jamal al-Din Muhammad bin Salem (d. 697 AH / 1299 AD), Mufarrej al-Karub fi Manaqib Bani Ayyub, investigation: Jamal al-Din al-Shayal, Fouad I University Press, (Cairo, 1953 AD), vol. 1, p. 139; Al-Ainy, Badr Al-Din Mahmoud bin Shihab Al-Din Ahmed (d. 855 AH / 1451 AD), the Juman contract in the history of the people of time, investigation: Mahmoud Rizk Mahmoud, 2nd edition, Dar al-Kutub and National Documents Press, (Cairo, 2010), Incidents (565-578 AH), part 1. , p. 78; Ibn Taghri Bardi, Jamal al-Din Abu al-Mahasin Youssef (874 AH / 1470 AD) The Shining Stars in the Kings of Egypt and Cairo, I 1, Dar al-Kutub al-Masryah, (Cairo, 1935 AD), vol. 5, p. 334; Al-Zarkali, Khair Al-Din bin Mahmoud bin Muhammad, Al-Alam, 15th edition, Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, (Beirut, 2002 AD), vol. 4, p. 147.
2. Turan Shah: He is the great Sultan Turan Shah, the son of Sultan Al-Malik Al-Salih Najm Al-Din Ayyub, son of the Sultan Al-Malik Al-Kamil Nasir Al-Din, the Sultan of the Egyptian lands, the Kurdish Ayyubid, the last king of Bani Ayyub. 1249 AD), and the Franks were beset by the soldiers of Islam. 1250 A.D.), God had conquered his hands and the victory of Islam over the Franks in the Battle of Al-Mansurah, so the people believed in his appearance and were glad to witness him, except that reasons appeared from him that repulsed hearts, so they agreed to kill him with the sympathy of his father's wife Shajar Al-Durr, because of his lightness, and it was said that he was corrupt and drank wine. His rule lasted less than a month, and it was said three months, until he was killed in a year (648 AH/1250AD). See: Sibte Ibn al-Jawzi, Shams al-Din Yusuf bin Qazogali (d. 654 AH / 1256 AD), the Mirror of Time in the History of the Notables, 1st Edition, the Ottoman Encyclopedia Press, (India, Hyderabad, Deccan, 1954 AD), vol. 8, vol. 2, p. 781; Al-Ghassani, Abu Al-Abbas Ismail bin Al-Abbas (803 AH / 1400 AD), the molten prostrate and the owned substance in the layers of caliphs and kings,

- investigation: Shaker Mahmoud Abdel Moneim, D, Dar Al Bayan, (Baghdad, 1975 AD), part 2, p. 576; Ibn Taghri Bardī, *Al-Nujūm Al-Zahirah*, Vol. 6, p. 322.
3. Shajar Al-Durr: A Turkish slave girl and an Armenian was said to have bought her by the good king Najm al-Din Ayyub and she bore him Hebron, but he died the life of a father, as she was a companion of the good sultan and returned to her with advice and opinion. She owned the Egyptian homes three months after his death in Qom, she was killed and buried near Mashhad al-Sayyida Nafisa. See: Abu Shama, Shihab al-Din Abd al-Rahman bin Ismail al-Maqdisi (665 AH / 1267 AD), the tail on the two kindergartens, investigation: Izzat Al-Shameen Al-Hasani, 2nd edition, Dar Al-Jeel, (Beirut, 1974 AD), vol. 3, part 5, p. 283; Ibn Taghri Bardī, *The Shining Stars*, Vol. 6, p. 91; Ibn Iyas, Abu al-Barakat Omar Ibn Ahmad (d. 923 AH / 1523 AD), *Badaa' al-Zohour fi Waqa'iq al-Daur*, investigation: Muhammad Mustafa Ziyada, Dar al-Kutub al-Arabiya, (Cairo, 1963 AD), vol. 1, volume 1, p. 294.
 4. Najm al-Din Ayyub al-Kurdi, originally from the Al-Hadhbaniyah tribe, was assigned to guard the Tikrit citadel for a period of years, and he had a good relationship with Imad al-Din Zangi. By order of the Zankien, he is the father of Saladin. See: Abu Shama, Shihab al-Din Abd al-Rahman bin Ismail al-Maqdisi (665 AH / 1267 AD), *Rawdatain fi Akhbar al-Dawlaan al-Nuriya wa al-Salihyyah*, investigation: Muhammad Helmy Muhammad, 1st Edition, Press, Authoring, Translation and Publishing Committee (Egypt, 1956), vol. 1, p. 320; Al-Maqrizi, Taqi Al-Din Abu Al-Abbas Ahmed bin Ali Al-Husseini (d. 845 AH / 1441 AD), *Behavior in the Knowledge of the Countries of Kings*, investigation: Muhammad Mustafa Ziada, Egyptian Book House Press, (Cairo, DT), vol. 6, p. 42.
 5. Mosul: a well-known city, one of the bases of Islam with few peers in its grandeur and grandeur, it is the gate of Iraq and the key to Khorasan, from which it is intended to Azerbaijan. It was called Mosul, because it reached between the island and Iraq, and it was said that it reached between the Tigris and the Euphrates, and it was said that it reached between the country of Sinjar and Haditha, he was the first to follow it Balamsar Marwan bin Mohammed, the last kings of the Umayyads. See: Yaqout al-Hamawi, Shihab al-Din Abi Abdullah al-Roumi (d. 626 AH / 1230 AD), *Mujam al-Buldan*, D, Dar Sader, (Beirut, 1977 AD), vol. 5, p. 223.
 6. Ibn Khalkan, Abu al-Abbas Ahmed bin Abi Bakr (d. 681 AH / 1282 AD), the deaths of notables and the news of the sons of time, investigation: Muhammad Muhyi al-Din Abdel Hamid, Cairo, (Al-Nahda Library, 1984 AD), vol. 2, p. 277.
 7. Nur al-Din Zangi: He is Abu al-Qasim Mahmoud bin Imad al-Din Zangi bin Aq Sanqar, nicknamed the just king Nur al-Din, and also nicknamed the martyr. He had great works in it, such as building schools, mosques, connections, and others. King Nur al-Din had a good handwriting, a lot of reading of religious books, following the prophetic traditions, reciting a lot, and keeping the prayers in congregations. He was brave and patient in war, setting an example. It was on Wednesday the eleventh of Shawwal in the year 569 AH / 1173 AD. He died at the age of fifty-eight years, and he was in the reign of twenty-eight years. He was buried in the Citadel of Damascus, and his grave is famous. See: Ibn Khalilkan, *Wayat al-A'yan*, vol. 5, p. 184; Al-Subki, Taj Al-Din Abdel-Wahhab Bin Ali (d. 771 AH / 1369 AD), *Tabaqat al-Shafi'i al-Kubra*, investigated by: Mahmoud Muhammad al-Tanahi, Abd al-Fattah Muhammad al-Hilu, 2nd edition, Hajar for printing and publishing, (Egypt, 1992), vol. 2, p. 32; Ibn Katheer, Amma Al-Din Abu Al-Fida Ismail Al-Qurashi Al-Dimashqi (d. 774 AH / 1372 AD), *The Beginning and the End*, investigation: Abdullah bin Abdul Mohsen Al-Turki, I 1, Hajar for printing, publishing, distribution and advertising, (Cairo, 1998 AD), vol. 16, pp. 480-493.
 8. Asad al-Din Shirkuwa: He is Abu al-Harith Shirkuh bin Shadi bin Marwan, and he is the uncle of Salah al-Din and one of the leaders of the Zangids. He was characterized by courage and bragging feet. He died in Egypt in the year (564 AH / 1168 AD) and his ministries lasted about two months and five days. See: Ibn Khallikan, *Wayat al-A'yan*, vol. 2, p. 317; Ibn Wasel, *Mufarrej Al-Karub*, Volume 1, p. 23.
 9. Ibn Wasil, *Mufarrej Al-Karub fi Manaqib Bani Ayyub*, vol. 1, p. 157.
 10. Ibn Kathir, *The Beginning and the End*, vol. 12, p. 307.
 11. Abu Shama, *Al-Rawdatain*, Part 1, pg. 160.
 12. Abu Shama, *Al-Rawdatain*, Part 1, pp. 183-184.
 13. Jeb, Hamilton, *Salah al-Din al-Ayyubi*, *Studies in Islamic History*, translated by: Youssef Ibish, The Arab Foundation for Studies and Publishing, (Beirut, 1973), p. 155.
 14. Abu al-Hija or al-Hija: He is Prince Hussam al-Din, one of the senior Kurdish princes, and the first deputy of Salah al-Din on Acre. In the year (585 AH / 1189 AD) the city of Nusaybin, then he was isolated from it due to the great injustice, and in the year (586 AH / 1190 AD), he was removed from the prosecution of Acre, he died (594 AH / 1197 AD). See: Abu Shama Al-Maqdisi, *Al-Rawdatain*, Volume 2, p. 70; Abu Shama, *The Tail on Al-Rawdatain*, p. 14-15.
 15. Abu Shama, *Al-Rawdatain*, Part 1, p. 174.

16. Trustee of the Caliphate: Jawhar, a black servant, known in history books by several names, including Jawhar al-Tushi, the chief of al-Tawashiya, and a trustee of the state and the caliphate. Saladin was not exposed and killed in the year (564 AH / 1169 AD). See: Abu Shama, *Al-Rawdatain*, Volume 1, Volume 2, pg. 450; Ibn Katheer, *Ismail bin Omar bin Katheer (774 AH / 1372 AD), The Beginning and the End*, vol. 13, p. 358, p. 435.
17. Ibn al-Atheer, Abu al-Hasan Ali ibn Abi al-Karam Muhammad ibn Abd al-Karim al-Shaibani al-Jazari (d. 630 AH / 1232 AD), *al-Kamel in History, investigation: Muhammad Yusuf al-Daqqaq*, 4th edition, *Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya (Beirut, 2003 AD)*, vol. 10, p. 18- 19.
18. 'Amara al-Yamani: He is the jurist Abu Muhammad 'Amara ibn Abi al-Hasan Ali al-Hakami al-Yamani, nicknamed Najm al-Din and a famous poet. In the year 569 AH / 1174 AD, he was referring to Balid al-Zaraji, the beginning of the country of Yemen. See: Ibn Khallikan, *Wayat al-A'yan*, vol. 3, pp. 431-435; Ibn Wasel, *Mufarrej Al-Karub*, Volume 1, p. 48; Al-Zahrani, *Marzouq bin Hayas, Attribution and Attribution*, 1st Edition, King Fahd National Library for Publishing, (Makkah Al-Mukarramah, 2014 AD), vol. 1, p. 454.
19. Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Suluk*, Volume 1, Volume 1, p. 54.
20. Hassan, Ali Ibrahim, *Egypt in the Middle Ages from the Arab Conquest to the Ottoman Conquest*, 4th Edition, *The Egyptian Renaissance Library*, (Cairo 1954), p. 178.
21. Ibn Wasil, *Mufarrej Al-Karub*, Volume 1, pp. 179-184.
22. Abu Shama, *Al-Rawdatain*, Part 1, p. 181.
23. Ibn Shaddad, *An-Nawadir*, p. 45.
24. Al-Malik Al-Salih Ismail: He is Imad Al-Din Ismail bin Nur Al-Din bin Mahmoud bin Zangi. He and his father were entrusted with the king. He was eleven years old on the day of his father's death. And Salah al-Din in Egypt, and he spoke to him, and the railway was struck in his name, and he was raised by Prince Shams al-Din Muhammad ibn Abd al-Malik, known as Ibn al-Muqaddam, and he became the administrator of his state. Except for Aleppo, and Al-Saleh Ismail remained there until he died in the year (577 AH / 1181 AD) when he was nineteen years old. alcohol or something else, until he died on that. See: Ibn al-Atheer, *al-Kamil fi al-Tarikh*, vol. 10, p. 58, pp. 106-107; Ibn Khallikan, *The Deaths of Notables*, vol. 5, p. 188.
25. Aleppo: a great city with vast bounties, good air, healthy skin and water, and it is the qasbah of Jund Qinnasrin. See: *Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of Countries*, Volume 2, pg. 282.
26. Ibn Wasil, *Mufarrej Al-Karub*, Volume 1, pp. 180-182.
27. Al-Mustiha' by the command of God: He is Abu Muhammad Al-Hasan bin Yusuf Al-Mustanajid bin Al-Muqtafi, the Abbasid Caliph who assumed the caliphate on the day of his father's death in the year 0 (566 AH / 1170 AD) and it continued until the year (577 AH / 1180 AD). Destiny, he dropped the tolls and taxes during his nine-year caliphate, and he is the one who returned the sermon in his name in the Egyptian lands, the Levant countries, and the frontiers after their interruption due to the hegemony of the Fatimid Caliphate. See: Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Suluk*, Part 1, p. 180; Al-Aini, *Contract of Juman, Incidents (565 AH-578 AH)*, p. 55.
28. Hassan, *Egypt in the Middle Ages*, p. 182.
29. Hittin: a village between Arsouf and Caesarea. See: *Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of Countries*, Volume 2, p. 273.
30. Jableh: a famous fortress on the coast of the Levant from the works of Aleppo near Latakia. See: *Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Mu'jam Al-Buldan*, Volume 2, p. 105.
31. Nablus: by the opening of the Nun and Alef, and the annexation of the united baa and the lam, and the neglected Sin at the end, and it is a city of the soldiers of Jordan, which needs it and does not need anything else, and there is no town in Palestine with running water except for it, and the rest of that its people drank from the rain and planted them on it, and in it there is the well that It was excavated by Jacob (peace be upon him), and on it is the mountain to which Samaria makes a pilgrimage. See: al-Qalqashandi, *Abu al-Abbas Ahmed bin Ali (d. 821 AH / 1418 AD), Subh al-Asha fi San'a al-Ansha*, Dr., *Dar al-Kutub al-Masryah*, (Cairo, 1922 AD), vol. 4, p. 103.
32. Acre: a country on the coast of the Levant Sea, built by Jordan, and it is a fortified city with a large mosque. See: *Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Mujam Al-Buldan*, Part 4, p. 143; Al-Qarmani, *Ahmed bin Youssef (d. 1019 AH / 1610 AD), News of the Countries and the Effects of the First in History, investigation: Ahmed Hoteit and Fahmy Saad*, 1st Edition, *World of Books*, (Beirut, 1992 AD), vol. 3, pg. 422.
33. Caesarea: A country on the coast of the Levant Sea is considered one of the works of Palestine. See: *Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of Countries*, Part 4, pg. 421.
34. Al-Ramla: a great city in Palestine, and its reed was ruined now, and it was a bond for Muslims, and a people of knowledge are attributed to it. See: *Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of Countries*, Part 3, pg. 69.

35. Jaffa: It is a city on the coast of the Levant Sea of Palestine between Caesarea and Acre in the third region. Its length on the west side is fifty-six degrees, and its width is thirty-three degrees. Jaffa is a country of drought. Al-Din when he conquered the coast in the year (583 AH / 1187 AD), then the Franks seized it in the year (587 AH / 1191 AD), then the just king Abu Bakr bin Ayyub restored it from them in the year (593 AH / 1196 AD), and destroyed it. See: Yaqout Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of Countries, Part 5, pg. 426.
36. Beirut: With the opening of the united baa and the sukoon of the ya' al-Muthanna under the inclusion of the neglected ra' and waw and ta' muthana above it at its end, it is a city from the third region on the coast of Damascus, and a great city on the bank of the Roman Sea, on it = two walls of stones, and in it there is a mountain in which there is metal of iron And it has a tip of pine trees, its capacity is twelve miles from the cracker, and it extends to the bottom of Lebanon. See: Al-Qalqashandi, Subh Al-Asha, Part 4, pp. 110-111.
37. Arsuf: a city on the coast of the Levant Sea, between Caesarea and Jaffa, in which there were a group of Almoravids, including Abu Yahya Zakaria bin Nafeh Al-Arsufi and others. It was in the hands of the Muslims until it was conquered by Kandfri, the owner of Jerusalem, in the year (494 AH/1101 AD), and it is in their hands until now. See: Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of Countries, Part 1, p. 151-152.
38. Ibn Taghri Bardi, Al-Nujoum Al-Zahira, Vol. 6, p. 31.
39. Richard: He is the King of England for the period (586-596 AH/1189-1199 AD). He grew up in a family whose essence was overshadowed by family disputes and betrayals. Richard's morals were not without serious defects. From a physical point of view, he was huge in body, tall, but strong in build. Red-haired, beautiful in character, he was a connoisseur of poetry, he derived from his parents a sharp temper and emotional will, but he did not inherit what his father was famous for in terms of political shrewdness and administrative competence. A very ambitious leader, he learned to be violent but not a loyal warrior, he was close to madness, he was distinguished by incredible courage and he was full of daring, and as a commander he was intelligent, prudent and cautious, and who could risk his life with complete indifference, he was only thirty-three years old. His age, until his fame preceded him to the East, died in the year (596 AH / 1199 AD). See: Runciman, Stephen, History of the Crusades, translated by: Al-Sayyid Al-Baz Al-Araini, House of Culture, (Beirut, 1997 AD), vol. 3, vol. 1, pp. 76-77; Mikhail, Zaborov, The Crusaders in the East, translated by: Elias Shaheen, Dar Al-Taqqaddam, (Moscow, 1986), footnote 1, p. 210.
40. Tyre: It is one of the most fortified city on the sea coast. It is full and fertile. It is said to be the oldest country on the coast. It is twelve miles between it and Acre. It was opened in the year six hundred and ninety with Acre and was ruined, and it is now an empty ruin. See: Abu Al-Fida, Al-Malik Al-Mu'ayyad Imad Al-Din Ismail (d. 732 AH / 1331 AD), Calendar of Countries, Correction: Raynaud Baron and Mac Cocken, D. T, Royal House, (Paris, 1850 AD), pp. 242-243.
41. Richard and his project was to establish peace and make peace with Bani Ayyub in that the just king, the brother of Saladin, would marry Queen Joanna, Richard's sister, on the condition that they would rule Jerusalem as its capital and that the priests and monks would be with her and that the two parties would release the prisoners and Richard would go to his country. See: Ibn Shaddad, Al-Anwadir Al-Sultaniyah, p. 195.
42. Hassan, Egypt in the Middle Ages, pp. 183-184.
43. Al-Dhahabi, Shams Al-Din Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Ahmed bin Othman Qaymaz (d. 748 AH / 1348 AD), the life of the media of the nobles, investigation: Shuaib Al-Arnaout and Muhammad Naim, Foundation of the Resala, (Beirut, 1992), vol. 12, p. 287.
44. Al-Aziz Othman: He is the dear King Othman Imad Al-Din Abu Al-Fath Othman, the Sultan of the Egyptian lands and the son of its sultan Al-Nasir Salah Al-Din Youssef, the son of Prince Najm Al-Din Ayoub bin Shadi Ibn Marwan Al-Kurdi, of Egyptian origin, and the ruler of the Sultanate of Egypt in the life of his father in an image, with the agreement of the princes and notables of the state in the land of Egypt. Because he was the representative of his father Salah al-Din in it when his father was busy opening the coasts in the Levant countries and he was commanded, his birth was in Cairo on the eighth Jumada al-Awwal in the year (567 AH / 1172 AD), and this dear king was younger than his brother, the Zahir Ghazi, the owner of Aleppo, and younger than his better brother. The owner of Damascus, he took the king of Egypt after the death of his father in the year (589 AH / 1193), and his just uncle resided on it, and the dear Othman is considered one of the wise people of this state, and he was very good and generous, and he had knowledge of hadith from the Salafi, Ibn Auf and Ibn Berri, and it happened, and the people loved him, and the people loved him He loved so much that things were straightened out in his days, and he was just in the parish, and he pardoned its money. He died in Cairo in the year (595AH/1198AD). See: Ibn al-Atheer, al-Kamil fi al-Tarikh, vol. 10, p. 157, 255, vol. 12, p. 54; Ibn Khallikan, The Deaths of Notable Persons, Volume 1, p. 314; Al-Maqrizi, Al-Suluk, Part 1, p.

- 114; Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahira*, Vol. 6, p. 120; Ibn Iyas, *Badaa' al-Zohour*, Volume 1, p. 73; Al-Zarkali, *Media*, Volume 4, p. 215.
45. Al-Afdal Ali: Abu Al-Hasan Ali, nicknamed King Al-Afdal, Nur al-Din bin Sultan Salah al-Din, born (565 AH/1169 AD), heard in Alexandria from Imam Abi al-Zahir Ismail Bani Makki, and in Egypt from the scholar Abu Muhammad bin Abdullah al-Nahwi, and Abu al-Hussein authorized him Ahmad Al-Salami, Abu Abdullah Muhammad Al-Harani and others, he wrote a good handwriting, he took his seat in the kingdom of Damascus and incidents took place with his dear brother and uncle Al-Malik Al-Adil, until they took Damascus from him and gave him Sarkad, then he resided in Sumaisat after the just king took Egypt, and he died there (622 AH / 1225 AD), and was transferred to Aleppo and was buried on the surface. See: Ibn Khalkan, *Wayat al-A'yan*, vol. 3, p. 419; Ibn Wasil, *Mufarrej Al-Karub*, Vol. 4, p. 155; Ibn Kathir, *The Beginning and the End*, vol. 13, p. 127; Sibt Ibn al-Jawzi, *Mirat al-Zaman*, Part 8, p. 637; Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahirah*, Vol. 6, p. 262; Ibn al-Imad al-Hanbali, *Abd al-Hayy ibn Ahmad al-Askari al-Dimashqi* (d. 1089 AH / 1678 AD), fragments of gold in *Akhbar Min Dahab*, investigation: Mahmoud Arnaout, I 1, Dar Ibn Kathir, (Beirut, 1991 AD), part 5, p. 101.
 46. The apparent king: Abu al-Fath and Abu Mansour Ghazi, son of Sultan Salah al-Din ibn Yusuf ibn Ayoub ibn Shadi, one of the kings of the Ayyubid state, born in Cairo in 568 AH / 1172 AD, and died in Aleppo in 613 AH / 1216 AD, due to a disease that afflicted him, and was entrusted with the king From after him to his son, the dear King Muhammad. See: Al-Aini, *Contract Al-Juman*, Incidents (590-615 AH), p. 298; Ibn Khallikan, *The Deaths of Notable Persons*, vol. 4, p. 6; Sibt Ibn al-Ajmi, *Abu Dhar Muwaffaq al-Din Ahmad ibn Ibrahim ibn Muhammad ibn Khalil* (d. 884 AH / 1479 AD), *Treasures of Gold in the History of Aleppo*, I 1, Dar al-Qalam, (Aleppo, 1996 AD), vol. 1, p. 106.
 47. The just king: Abu Bakr Muhammad bin Abi Al-Shakr Ayoub bin Shadhi bin Marwan, nicknamed the just king Sayf al-Din, born in (540 AH / 1146 AD), and it was said: (538 AH / 1144 AD), and he is the brother of Sultan Salah al-Din, he grew up in the service of Nur al-Din The martyr was with his father and brothers, he attended with his brother Salah al-Din his conquests and conquests, and he was in charge of him in the Egyptian lands, then he gave him Aleppo and Karak and his works. Many matters until the king settled for him, leaving seventeen sons, among whom were al-Kamil, al-Ma'azm, al-Ashraf, al-Salih, and Shihab al-Din, who died at the age of seventy, in the year 615 AH/1218. See: Al-Dhahabi, *Sir Flags of the Nobles*, Part 22, pp. 116-119; Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Suluk*, Vol. 1, p. 309; Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahira*, Vol. 6, p. 199; Ibn al-Imad al-Hanbali, vol. 7, p. 117.
 48. Diyar Bakr: It is related to Bakr bin Wael. It alone is west of the Tigris to the mountainous country overlooking Nusaybin to the Tigris, including the fortress of Kiva, Amed and Mayafaraqin. See: Yaqout Al-Hamawi, *Dictionary of Countries*, Volume 2, pg. 494.
 49. Baalbek: With the conquest of the monotheistic baa and the silence of the neglected eye, the conquest of al-Lam and al-Ba', the monotheistic and the second, and at the end of it is sufficient. It is an old building, it is said that it is from the building of Solomon (peace be upon him). See: Al-Qalqashandi: *Subh Al-Asha*, Part 4, pp. 109-110.
 50. Homs: a famous ancient and large walled country with a large and fortified castle, on a high hill between Damascus and Aleppo in the middle of the road. See: Yaqout Al-Hamawi, *Dictionary of Countries*, Part 4, p. 143.
 51. Hama: a large city with many bounties, full of markets, surrounded by a tight wall. The wall appears to be a very large present in which there are many markets and a mosque that overlooks its river known as the Orchard, which has water wheels that water its orchards and pour into the pool of the mosque, and on its outskirts is a great castle. See: Yaqout Al-Hamawi, *Dictionary of Countries*, Volume 2, pg. 300.
 52. Hassan, *Egypt in the Middle Ages*, p. 186.
 53. Ibn al-Skeet, *Abu Yusuf Yaqoub bin Ishaq al-Ahwazi* (d. 244 AH/867 AD), *Arranging the Reform of Logic*, presented by Sheikh Muhammad Hassan al-Bakai, 1st Edition, Astana Printing and Publishing Institution, (Tehran, 1992 AD), p. 365.
 54. Al-Razi, *Muhammad bin Abi Bakr bin Abdul Qadir* (died after 666 AH / 1106 AD) *Mukhtar Al-Sahah*, investigation: Mahmoud Khatra, 1st edition, Library of Lebanon Publishers, (Beirut, 1995), p. 642.
 55. Ibn Manzur, *Jamal al-Din Abu al-Fadl Muhammad bin Makram bin Ali* (d. 711 AH / 1311 AD), *Lisan al-Arab*, an illustrated edition of the Bulaq Press, (Cairo, D. T.), vol. 2, p. 383.
 56. *Surat An-Nisa*, verse 36.
 57. Al-Fayrouz Abadi, *Majd Al-Din Muhammad bin Yaqoub* (d. 817 AH / 1414 AD), *Al-Mutih Dictionary*, Al-Maimani Press, (Cairo, 1902 AD), vol. 3, p. 330; Al-Bustani, *Boutros*, Ocean Ocean, Jawad Corporation Press, (Beirut - 1977), vol. 1, p. 682.
 58. Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Suluk*, Part 1, p. 122.
 59. Ashour, Said, *Systems of Governance and Administration in the Age of the Ayyubids and Mamluks*, *Encyclopedia of Arab-Islamic Civilization*, (Beirut, 1980), p. 16.

60. Al-Khoury, Jules Qazali, *The Syrians in Egypt, the Syrian Edition*, (Damascus, 1928 AD), vol. 1, volume 1, p. 78.
61. Al-Qafjaq: a region in the Volga River Basin, north of the Caucasus Mountains, which follows the Russian and Khazar seas. Its inhabitants are of Turkish origin and from which the region derives its name, and their country is an important center for the white slave trade from the Turks. They were famous for their equestrianism, courage, and beauty of image. See: Al-Astakhri, Ibn Ishaq Ibrahim bin Muhammad Al-Farsi Al-Karkhi (d. 346 AH / 957 AD), *Masalak Al-Mamluk*, investigation: Muhammad Jaber Abdel-Al, 1st edition, Dar Al-Qalam, (Cairo, 1961), pp. 128-132; Al-Qalqashandi, *Subh Al-Asha*, Part 4, pg. 458.
62. The Caucasus: They are called Alan, the end of which is Nun: a vast country on the edge of Armenia, near the door of the Gates, adjacent to the Khazars. See: Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, *Mujam Al-Buldan*, Part 5, p. 8.
63. Yaqoot al-Hamawi, *Mu'jam al-Buldan*, Volume 2, p. 379; Ashour, Said Abdel-Fattah, *The Ayyubids and the Mamluks in Egypt and the Levant*, Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, (Cairo, 1996), p. 177.
64. Al-Dhahabi, *Biography of the Nobles*, vol. 10, p. 293; Al-Maqrizi, Taqi al-Din Abi al-Abbas Ahmed bin Ali (d. 845 AH / 1441 AD), *sermons and consideration in remembrance of plans and effects*, D, Egyptian General Foundation, (Cairo, 1963 AD), vol. 2, p. 69; Hassan, Ali Ibrahim, *Studies in the History of the Maritime Mamluks and in the Era of Al-Nasir Muhammad in particular*, D., The Egyptian Renaissance Library, (Cairo, 1944 AD), p. 30.
65. Damietta: An ancient city between Tennis and Egypt, on a corner between the Roman Sea. See: Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, *Dictionary of Countries*, Volume 2, pg. 472.
66. The jalab and the robbers: the jalab, they are young slaves who are bought by the sultan and who raises them. As for the jalabans, they are the adult slaves who enter the country stealthily, then the sultan agrees to their entry or they enter at the will of the sultan, and in both cases they are considered the kings of the sultan, and some of them may make soldiers in the circle . See: Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahira*, Volume 7, pg. 386; Al-Qalqashandi, *Subh Al-Asha*, Part 4, pg. 16.
67. Ibn Iyas, *Badaa' al-Zohour fi Waqa'iyat al-Daur*, vol. 3, p. 21.
68. The Circassians: their origins go back to the Circassian people, and their homeland is located in Siberia, north of the continent of Asia, specifically in the regions of Lake Began, where they came to the areas west of the Caspian Sea in the sixth century AD. look:Hitti, Philip, *History of the Arabs*, Dar al-Kutub, 4th edition, (Beirut, DT), vol. 5, p. 4, and 795.
69. Ibn Abd al-Zahir, Muhyi al-Din Abu al-Fadl Abdullah Rashid al-Din Ibn Safwan al-Masri (d. 692 AH / 1929 AD), *Honoring the Days and Ages in the Biography of King Mansour*, investigation: Murad Kamel, Ministry of Culture and National Guidance, (Cairo - 1961 AD), Introduction The investigator, p. 37; Ibn Khaldun, Abd al-Rahman Muhammad al-Hadrami (d. 808 AH / 1405 AD), *The Lessons and Diwan of the Beginner and the News in the Days of Arabs, Non-Arabs, Berbers and Their Contemporaries with the Greatest Sultan*, D., Al-Azami Foundation, (Beirut, 1291 AH), vol. 2, p. 369.
70. Al-Qalqashandi, *Subh Al-Asha fi San'a Al-Ansha*, Volume 2, pp. 15-17; Al-Arini, Al-Sayyid Al-Baz, *The Mamluks*, Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, (Beirut - 1967 AD), pp. 72-75.
71. Tabaq: its singular layer, which is the barracks of the Sultanate Mamluks, and the responsible for it is called Tabaq. They are places designated as housing for Mamluks, training, mobilizing and preparing them to take over jobs. Each layer includes the sons of the same sex from the Mamluks. See: Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Khitat*, Volume 2, pp. 346-347; C3, pp. 65-66.
72. Al-Khashdasha, the plural of the khadash, meaning the fellow in the service, and they are the ones who grew up as Mamluks with one master, so a bond of fellowship was built between them. See: Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Suluk*, Part 1, p. 388, footnote 3; Al-Arini, *The Mamluks*, p. 211.
73. First, the education of the young Mamluks begins with the drawing of writing and Islamic rituals from memorizing the Qur'an, hadith, jurisprudence, calligraphy, Sharia etiquette and prayer, then training them in martial arts and horsemanship, after which they are freed from slavery and their personal loyalty to their master who bought them. See: Al-Maqrizi, *Al-Khitat*, vol. 2, p. 313.
74. The Tulunid State: It belongs to its founder, Ahmed bin Tulun, the Turkic Ghazi in Egypt in 254 AH / 868 AD and extended to include the Levant and the Hijaz, one of the countries that became independent from the Abbasid Caliphate in Baghdad, and Ibn Tulun ruled for the years from 254-292 AH / 868-905 AD), and the Tulunid state represents the first to use the Mamluks in Egypt until their number reached a thousand Mamluks. See: Ibn Iyas, *Badaa' al-Zuhur fi Waqa'iyat al-Daur*, vol. 1, p. 27; Taqosh, Muhammad Suhail, *History of the Tulunids, the Ikhshidids and the Hamdanids*, 1st Edition, Dar Al-Nafais, (Beirut, 2008), p. 6.
75. Al-Aini, *Aqd Al-Juman*, Part 4, pg. 4; Al-Abadi, Ahmed Mukhtar, *The Establishment of the Early Mamluk State in Egypt and the Levant*, Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya (Beirut, 1969), p. 70.

76. Abu Jaafar al-Mansur: He is the Caliph, Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Ali al-Hashimi al-Abbasid al-Mansur, and his mother is Salama al-Barbari. Light-weighted, blotchy, broad forehead, as if his eyes were speaking tongues, the pomp of the king mingled with hermit's dress, accepted by hearts and followed by eyes, the nose was darker, and he was dyed with blackness. The second Abbasid, who is the founder of the Abbasid Caliphate, was the stud of Bani Abbas with prestige, courage, cunning and tyranny, full of mind and good participation in jurisprudence and literature. Prayers and goodness. He was spending money in the feared Kufa, especially when Muhammad bin Abdullah bin Hassan revolted against him in Medina and his brother Ibrahim in Basra, and he was the builder of Baghdad, the capital of the Abbasid Caliphate for the period (145-149 AH / 762-766 AD), who was the ruler of all the kingdoms of Islam except for the island of Andalusia. He used to look at the wretched of money, make it fruitful, and strive hard so that he left behind In the two cash houses, there were fourteen thousand dinars, according to what was said, and six hundred thousand thousand dirhams, and he was very similar to the three in his policies and his package, and they are, Muawiyah bin Abi Sufyan, Abdul Malik bin Marwan, and Hisham bin Abdul Malik. The Caliph Abu Jaafar died and lived Sixty-four years ago, he was buried between Al-Hujun and Well Maimouna in Dhul-Hijjah, 158AH/775AD. See: al-Tabari, Abi Jaafar Muhammad ibn Jarir (310 AH / 923 AD), the history of the messengers and kings, known as the history of al-Tabari, investigation: Muhammad Abu al-Fadl Ibrahim, 4th edition, Dar al-Maaref, (blood, 1977 AD), vol. 7, p. 471; Ibn al-Atheer, al-Kamil fi al-Tarikh, vol. 5, pp. 461-462; Al-Dhahabi, Sir Flags of the Nobles, vol. 7, pp. 83-89.
77. Asbhabd: A foreign name, given by the rulers of Persia to those who entrust him with the rule of Tabaristan until his death, and he is assigned after him if he has a son, and if they do not choose him, they are the kings of Oman and Bahrain. See: Ibn Manzur, Lisan al-Arab, vol. 3, pg. 477; Al-Zubaidi, Muhammad Murtada Al-Hussaini, (1205 AH / 1790 AD) The Crown of the Bride from the Jewels of the Dictionary, investigation: Abdul Sattar Ahmed Farraj, Arab Heritage House, (Kuwait, 1971 AD), vol. 9, pp. 434-435.
78. Al-Jumaili, Rashid Abdullah, Sidon in the Mamluk Era, Echo of History, (magazine) Sixth Issue, (Baghdad - 2000), p. 241.
79. Al-Hajjaj bin Artah Al-Kufi: He is Hajjaj bin Arta' bin Hubayrah bin Sharahabil Al-Nakh'i Al-Qadi and one of the senior followers of the followers of the seventh class. He died in the year 145 AH / 762 AD), in Khorasan. He heard from Ata bin Abi Rabah, and he narrated on the authority of Sufyan Al-Thawri, Ibn Al-Mubarak and others He was with the Caliph Abu Jaafar al-Mansur during the construction of the city of Baghdad, and is considered the first governor of Basra district. See: Ibn Khalilkan, Wayat al-A'yan, Volume 2, pp. 52, 54, 55; Al-Dhahabi, Sir Flags of the Nobles, Volume 7, pp. 68-72.69-74.
80. Al-Baladhari, Ahmed bin Yahya bin Jaber Al-Baghdadi (d. 279 AH/892 AD), Fotouh al-Buldan, investigation: Radwan Muhammad Radwan, Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya, (Beirut, 1403 AH), p. 127.
81. Selim, Mahmoud Rizk, The Age of the Mamluk Sultans and its Scientific and Literary Production, Library of Arts (Cairo - 1947), vol. 1, volume 1, p. 15.
82. Metz, Adam, Islamic Civilization in the Fourth Hijri Century, Translated by Muhammad Abd al-Wahhab, Abu Rabdeh, (Cairo - 1957 AD), ed 2, vol. 2, p. 226.
83. Dar al-Raqib: a locality in Baghdad connected to the al-Tahri harem from the western side, and it is now al-Mahalla Street, with the market in it. See: Ibn Abd al-Haq, Safi al-Din Abd al-Mumin ibn Abd al-Haq al-Baghdadi (d. 739 AH / 1338 AD), observatories to see the names of places and the Bekaa, investigation, Muhammad al-Bajawi, House of Revival of Arabic Books, (Damascus - 1954 AD), Vol. 2, p. 505.
84. Al-Abadi, Ahmed Mukhtar, The Establishment of the Mamluk State in Egypt and the Levant, p. 226.
85. Al-Khazraji, Zainab Hatem, The Damascene Society in the Mamluk Era, a master's thesis in Islamic history, presented to the Council of the College of Education, Al-Mustansiriya University (Baghdad - 2001), p. 15.
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87. The Ikhshidid State: It belongs to its founder, Muhammad ibn Tughaj ibn Jaf ibn Belkin ibn Furan ibn Fauri ibn Khaqan al-Ikhshid al-Turki, the owner of the Golden Bed, one of the provinces of the Caspian Sea. Years after the return of Egypt, the Levant and the Hijaz to Abbasid sovereignty, after the collapse of the Tulunid state, which independent of the Abbasid Caliphate, the Abbasid Caliph Radi God (322-329 AH / 934-940 AD) appointed Muhammad bin Tughaj as governor of Egypt, and he established safety and eliminated the rebels on The Abbasid Caliphate, the Abbasid Caliph gave him the title (Al-Akhshid) in honor of his efforts in the year 326AH/937AD. He took Egypt from the Abbasid Caliphate and seized the Levant and the Hejaz. See: Yaqoot Al-Hamawi, Dictionary of

- Countries, Part 3, pp. 218-219; Al-Maqrizi, *The Plans*, Part 1, p. 329; Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahira*, Vol. 3, p. 244; Kashef, *Lady Ismail, Egypt during the Ikhshidid Era*, Fouad I Press, (Cairo, 1950), pp. 55-77.
88. Al-Kindi, Abu Omar Muhammed bin Youssef Al-Masry, (d. 350 AH / 961 AD), Governor of Egypt, I 1, Cultural Books Foundation, (Beirut, 1987 AD), p. 205.
 89. Al-Hijriya: It was named by this name in relation to the places where the Mamluks resided in rooms numbering seven. Later, of course, the origin of their use goes back to the Abbasid Caliph Al-Mutadid (279-289 AH/892-902AD), who used them for special guarding and protection, and he is the one who named them as Al-Hijriyah. See: Ibn Abd al-Zahir, *Sahib Muhyi al-Din Abu al-Fadl al-Masri* (d. 692 AH / 1292 AD), the radiant kindergarten in the plans of the condolence Cairo, investigation: Ayman Fouad al-Sayed, i. 1, Dar al-Arabiya, (Cairo, 1996), p. 51.
 90. The Kurds or Kurds: a Muslim people living and concentrated in the region of the Euphrates Island and its surrounding countries such as Turkey, Iraq, Syria and Armenia. In the Middle Ages, the term Kurds was used to refer to nomadic and pastoral groups. See: Al-Bakri, Abu Obaid Abdullah bin Abdul-Aziz Al-Andalusi (487 AH/1095AD), *Paths and Kingdoms*, investigation: Adrian van Leeuwen, Andre Ferry, D., *Dar al-Gharb al-Islami*, (blood, 1992 AD), vol. 1, p. 343; Ibn Hawqal al-Nusabi, Abu al-Qasim Muhammad ibn Ali al-Baghdadi (367 AH / 977 AD), *Surat al-Ard*, D, Dar Sader, (Beirut, 1938 AD), vol. 2, p. 370.
 91. Al-Bandari, Al-Fath Bin Ali (d. 639 AH / 1182 AD), Sana Al-Barq Al-Shami, investigation: Fathiya Al-Nabrawi, D., Al-Khanji Library, (Cairo, 1979), pp. 41-42.
 92. Ibn Duqmaq, Ibrahim bin Aydmr Al-Ala'i, (d. 809 AH / 1399 AD), *The Precious Essence in the Lives of Kings and Sultans*, investigation: Muhammad Kamal al-Din, World of Books, 1st Edition, (Beirut - 1985 AD), vol. 1, p. 192.
 93. Al-Khwarizmiya: It is related to the province of Khwarezm on the Jayhon River, and it is one of the Islamic sects settled in the province of Khwarizm Shah, and it is several families, the most famous of which is the Anushtkin family. Ala al-Din bin Qutb al-Din to be independent in the region because of the weakness of the Seljuks in the year (532 AH / 1138 AD), which obtained from the Abbasid Caliph al-Muqtafi Amr Allah (530-555 AH / 1136-1160 AD) an authorization to rule after the weakness of the Seljuks, and this state collapsed at the hands of Genghis Khan in the year (618 AH / 1220 AD). See: Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahirah*, Vol. 6, p. 286; Al-Aboud, Nafeh Tawfiq, *The Khwarizm State, Its Origins and Its Relationship with Islamic Countries, Its Military and Administrative Systems*, University Press, (Baghdad 1978), pp. 11-13.
 94. Al-Mu'tasim Al-Abbasid: He is the Commander of the Faithful, Abu Ishaq Muhammad Al-Mu'tasim, the son of the Commander of the Faithful, Harun Al-Rashid, the son of the Commander of the Faithful, the Mahdi Muhammad bin the Commander of the Faithful, Abi Jafar Abdullah Al-Mansur bin Muhammad bin Ali bin Abdullah bin Al-Abbas. Among them is that he is the eighth of the caliphs from his descendants, and among them is that he conquered eight conquests of the country of Babak at the hands of Al-Afshin and Amoriyah himself, Al-Zat Ba'ajif, the Basra sea, the Citadel of Al-Jarf, the Bedouins of the homes of Rabi'ah, and Al-Sharek, and the conquest of Egypt after its disobedience, and the killing of eight enemies, Babak, Mazyaar, and Yatus Al-Rumi Al-Afshin, Ajifa, and compare, and among them is that he resided in the caliphate for eight years, eight months, and eight days, and it was said and two days, and that he was born in the year one hundred and eighty in Sha'ban, which is the eighth month, and that he died at the age of forty-eight years, including that he left eight sons and eight daughters, including that he entered Baghdad from the Levant while he was a caliph at the beginning of Ramadan in the eighteenth year, and two hundred after completing eight months of the year, after the death of his brother Al-Mamoun Petrosos, as mentioned above, and they said he was illiterate and could not write, and the reason for that was that he frequented with him to The book is a boy, so he died to a boy, so his father Al-Rasheed said to him, "What did your boy do?" He said, "He died and rested from the book." His father, Al-Rashid, said to him, "You have reached the point of hating the book until you make death a rest from him. By God, do not go to the book after that, so they left him, so he was illiterate, and it was said that he used to write in writing." Weak, and it was said that the king of the Romans wrote a letter to al-Mu'tasim threatening him, so he said to the scribe, "Write, I have read your book, and I heard your speech, and the answer is what you see, not what you hear." In the enemy, and he set fireboats on Amoriyah, and he stayed on it until he opened it and entered it, killing thirty thousand in it, and captivating the like of them. The mosque is next to the mosque in the palace, and when he assumed the caliphate, he was chivalrous in his days and had a high determination, and a very great fear. Close to twenty thousand, and it was made of war machines and To animals that were not agreed upon by anyone else, and when death approached him, he began to say that even if they were happy with what they were given, we seized them suddenly, and then they were despondent, and he said, If I knew that my life was short, I would not have done what I did. On the authority of him,

he said in the illness of his death, O God, I fear You before me, and I do not fear You before You, and I hope for You before You, and I do not hope from You before me. Two hundred and twenty, and his birth was on the Monday of the tenth of Sha'ban in the year one hundred and eighty, and he became the caliph in the month of Rajab in the year two hundred and eighty. Each of them is named Muhammad, and they are Abu Ishaq al-Mu'tasim, Abu al-Abbas al-Amin, Abu Issa, Abu Ahmad, Abu Yaquob, and Abu Ayyub, and his son Harun al-Wathiq rose to the caliphate after him. See: Ibn al-Atheer, *al-Kamil fi al-Tarikh*, vol. 6, p. 525; Al-Dhahabi, *Sir Flags of the Nobles*, vol. 10, p. 290; Ibn Katheer, *The Beginning and the End*, Vol. 14, pp. 283-288.

95. Ibn Duqmaq, *The Precious Essence in the Lives of Kings and Sultans*, Volume 1, p. 98.
96. The vestibule: It is the tent that accompanies the sultan and is self-contained, meaning that there are no other tents on its sides. See: Al-Ayni, *Aqd Al-Juman fi Tarikh Ahl Al-Zaman*, Part 4, pg. 9.
97. Ibn Ibak, Abu Bakr bin Abdullah Al-Dawdari (d. 732 AH / 1335 AD), the treasure of al-Durar and the Mosque of al-Gharar, al-Durar required in the news of Bani Ayyub, investigation by: Said Abdel Fattah Ashour, d. T, DM, (Cairo, 1927 AD), C 7, pg. 373.
98. Al-Rawda Island: It is one of the places of Al-Fustat, but it was called Al-Jazirah because the Nile, if it overflowed, surrounded it and the water came between it and most of the lands of Al-Fustat. See: Ibn Taghri Bardi, Abu al-Mahasin Jamal al-Din Yusuf (874 AH / 1469 AD), *Incidents of Eternity in the Range of Days and Months*, investigation: William Boyer, d. T., DM, (California, 1931 AD), vol.3, p. 450.
99. The Bahari Mamluks: They are the sultans who ruled Egypt and the Levant, where they numbered 28 sultan and were named in the navy in relation to the Nile Sea, which surrounded their barracks on the island of Rawda, which they inhabited. See: Ibn Taghri Bardi, *Al-Nujoum Al-Zahira*, Vol. 4, p. 90.
100. Al-Diyar Bakri, Hussein bin Hamad bin Al-Hassan (d. 982 AH / 1574 AD), the history of Thursday in *Ahwal Al-Nafis*, d., Dar Al-Kitab Al-Arabi for Printing and Publishing, (Cairo 1942 AD), vol. 2, p. 118.

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